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REVIEW ON QUINOLINE ANALOGS AS POTENTIAL ANTI-HIV AGENTS

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ABSTRACT

The human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) has now been established as the causative agent of the acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS). The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved anti-HIV drugs and divided into seven groups. However, the use of these drugs has been relatively limited by their toxicity, drug resistance development. New anti-HIV drugs with acceptable toxicity, less resistance profiles and with novel mechanisms of action are clearly needed. Here HIV replication cycle, Possible HIV Targets and Interventions, Global situation and trends, approved antiretroviral drugs are discussed. This marked the beginning of the era of highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART). However future anti-HIV drug research efforts focused on new HIV targets such as HIV proteins and RNase H. Various modifications done on quinoline scaffold, to search for lead molecule is also described.

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INTRODUCTION

Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) is a group of symptoms and infections originated from the damage to the specific immune system caused by infection with the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) which is termed as retrovirus of the lentivirus family originally referred as HTLV-III. It results from the latter stages of advanced HIV infection in humans; thereby leaving compromised individuals prone to opportunistic infections and tumors. AIDS is the most severe manifestation of infection with HIV. HIV is a retrovirus that primarily infects vital components of the human immune system such as CD4+ T cells, macrophages and dendritic cells. It directly and indirectly destroys CD4+ T cells. CD4+ T cells are required for the proper functioning of the immune system. When HIV kills CD4+ T cells so that there are less than 200 CD4+ T cells per μl blood, cellular immunity is lost, leading to AIDS. People with AIDS often suffer infections of the lungs, intestinal tract, brain, eyes, and other organs, as well as debilitating weight loss, diarrhea, neurologic conditions, and cancers such as Kaposi's sarcoma and certain types of lymphomas.

The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved anti-HIV drugs and divided into seven groups: nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NRTIs), nucleotide reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NRTIs), non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIs), protease inhibitors (PIs), fusion inhibitors (FIs), co-receptor inhibitors (CRIs), and integrase inhibitors (INIs). This arsenal of drugs, which is used in combinations, has moved the prognosis of HIV patients from that of high morbidity and mortality to, for many at least, a chronic, manageable but still complex disease. However, the use of these drugs is relatively limited by their toxicity, drug resistance development, and more worryingly, the fact that some newly HIV-infected patients carry viruses that are already resistant to the currently approved AIDS treatments. These issues along with drug-related side effects as well as, in some cases, poor tolerability of these drugs made it apparent that new anti-HIV drugs with acceptable toxicity and less resistance profiles with novel mechanisms of action are clearly needed [1,2]. Some of the possible HIV targets and interventions are described below in table 1 with replication cycle of HIV in figure 1.

Table 1. Summary of the Possible HIV Targets and Interventions [2].

stage of HIV lifecycle	potential intervention
Binding to target cell	Antibodies to the virus or cell receptor
Early entry to target cell	Drugs that block fusion or interfere with retroviral uncoating
Transcription of RNA to DNA by reverse transcriptase	Reverse transcriptase inhibitors
Degradation of viral RNA in the RNA-DNA hybrid	Inhibitors of RNase H activity
Integration of DNA into the host genome	Drugs that inhibit "integrase" function
Expression of viral genes	"Antisense" constructs; inhibitors of the tat protein or art/trs protein
Viral component production and assembly	Myristoylation, glycosylation, and protease inhibitors
Budding of virus	Interferons

The replication cycle of HIV [3].

Nature Reviews | Microbiology

Figure 1. HIV replication cycle. The basic steps of the HIV replication cycle: viral entry, reverse transcription, integration, and formation of infectious particles.

Global situation and trends:

Since the beginning of the epidemic, more than 70 million people have been infected with the HIV virus and about 35 million people have died of HIV. Globally, 36.7 million [34.0–39.8 million] people were living with HIV at the end of 2015. An estimated 0.8% [0.7–0.9%] of adults aged 15–49 years worldwide are living with HIV, although the burden of the epidemic continues to vary considerably between countries and regions. Sub-Saharan Africa remains most severely affected, with nearly 1 in every 25 adults (4.4%) living with HIV and accounting for nearly 70% of the people living with HIV worldwide. The figures was adapted from the link <http://www.who.int/gho/hiv/en>

36.7 million people are living with HIV around the world

Source: UNAIDS, 2016 estimates.

Improvements are needed at each stage of the cascade of HIV testing and treatment services, 2015

Source: UNAIDS/WHO estimates.

Number of people newly infected with HIV

Source: UNAIDS/WHO estimates. The red shading shows future targets.

Number of people dying from HIV

Source: UNAIDS/WHO estimates. The red shading shows future targets.

Global summary of the AIDS epidemic | 2015

Number of people living with HIV in 2015	Total	36.7 million [34.0 million – 39.8 million]
	Adults	34.9 million [32.4 million – 37.9 million]
	Women (15+)	17.8 million [16.4 million – 19.4 million]
	Children (<15 years)	1.8 million [1.5 million – 2.0 million]
People newly infected with HIV in 2015	Total	2.1 million [1.8 million – 2.4 million]
	Adults	1.9 million [1.7 million – 2.2 million]
	Children (<15 years)	150 000 [110 000 – 190 000]
AIDS deaths in 2015	Total	1.1 million [940 000 – 1.3 million]
	Adults	1.0 million [840 000 – 1.2 million]
	Children (<15 years)	110 000 [84 000 – 130 000]

WHO – HIV department | June 15, 2016

Global Prevalence of HIV in 2015

As discussed above, the HIV develops resistance against individual drugs and inhibitors. To solve this problem a new pharmaceutical strategy was developed which involved combining several antiretroviral compounds. This approach benefited the most from the development of drugs in NNRTIs and PI classes. Combination therapy blocked the resistance effect more effectively for two reasons; first, multiple mechanisms are required for resistance to occur to all drugs in the regimen and second; multiple drugs suppress viral replication more effectively than single agents. This marked the beginning of the era of highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) in 1995. HAART combines a minimum of three drugs from at least two different drug classes targeting distinct proteins. A typical HAART treatment combines two NRTIs plus either one PI or one NNRTI [4,1]. Combinations of antiretrovirals create multiple barriers to the HIV replication process. This helped to keep the number of offspring low and reduce the possibility of a superior mutation.

In 2006, it was reported that the number of HIV related deaths declined due to HAART treatment. Despite the increasing concerns regarding antiretroviral resistance, the death rate among HIV-infected people continued to decline [5,6]. HAART suffers from certain limitations, despite of its success. HAART therapy is highly effective in delaying the onset of AIDS but its clinical utility is limited by viral resistance, non-adherence to therapy, and drug toxicity. Consequently, multidrug regimens are necessary for successful treatment. Since each HAART agent has its own unique adverse effect profile, selecting a regimen with a favorable profile may be difficult. Some of the approved antiretroviral drugs are reported in table 2.

Table 2. Approved antiretroviral drugs [7].

Generic Name	Brand Name	Manufacturer
Zalcitabine	Hivid	Hoffmann-La Roche
Stavudine	Zerit	Bristol-Myers Squibb
Lamivudine	Epivir	GlaxoSmithKline
Saquinavir	Invirase (hard gel capsule)	Hoffmann-La Roche
Ritonavir	Norvir	Abbott Laboratories
Indinavir	Crixivan	Merck
Nevirapine	Viramune	Boehringer Ingelheim
Nelfinavir	Viracept	Agouron Pharmaceuticals
Delavirdine	Rescriptor	Pfizer
Efavirenz	Sustiva (USA)	Bristol-Myers Squibb
Zidovudine	Retrovir	GlaxoSmithKline
Didanosine	Videx (tablet)	Bristol-Myers Squibb
Enfuvirtide	Fuzeon	Hoffmann-La Roche & Trimeris
Atazanavir	Reyataz	Bristol-Myers Squibb
Emtricitabine	Emtriva	Gilead Sciences
Fosamprenavir	Lexiva (USA)	GlaxoSmithKline
Tipranavir	Aptivus	Boehringer Ingelheim
Darunavir	Prezista	Tibotec, Inc.
Maraviroc	Celsentri (Europe)	Pfizer
Raltegravir	Isentress	Merck & Co., Inc.
Etravirine	Intence	Tibotec Therapeutics

There is no doubt that, since the discovery of HIV many years ago, the progress made toward developing effective anti-HIV therapies. This progress generated an armamentarium of anti-HIV drugs, which target several different stages of the HIV life cycle. This, therefore, has enabled the use of combination therapy in combating HIV infections. Although the drugs making up these treatment regimens have proved effective, some problems such as toxicity and resistance development have limited their use and prompted the search for new agents. The new anti-HIV drugs is well stocked that are going to be “nextgeneration” drugs. However, as we highlighted in this work, future anti-HIV drug research efforts and it focused on new HIV targets such as HIV proteins and RNase H. Various modifications were done on quinoline scaffold, to search for lead molecule as described below.

Substitutions on Quinoline Nucleus and anti-HIV Activity:

Luo Zai-gang et al reported the lead compound obtained through virtual screening by considering the structure of the integrase core domain and pharmacophore perception and synthesized a series of analogues of the following compound. Their anti-HIV properties against integrase demonstrated that 6-position methyl group on the benzene ring of quinolone important than chlorine and methyl group at 7-position or no substituted group. But compounds shown little difference with substituted group such as phenyl or thienyl on the pyridine ring of quinoline [8].

2-(thiophen-2-yl)-N-(3-(4-(3-(2-(thiophen-2-yl)quinoline-5-carboxamido)propyl)piperazin-1-yl)propyl)quinoline-4-carboxamide

Lead Compound

Nafees Ahmed et al described naturally occurring quinolone alkaloids, buchupine and other compounds previously synthesized and reported as anti-HIV potential compound in human CD4+ T cell line CEM-GFP, infected with HIV-1NL4.3 virus by p24 antigen capture ELISA assay. Further, many alkylated derivatives of quinoline 2, 4-diol were synthesized and tested for anti-HIV potential. Following compound was found to be more potent than previously synthesized buchupine compounds and had better therapeutic index as compared to other drugs. Other derivatives have also shown good noticeable anti-HIV activity [9].

Potent Compound 3,3-bis(3-methylbut-2-en-1-yl)quinoline-2,4(1H,3H)-dione

Dharmarajan Sriram et al for the effective treatment of AIDS designed a amino pyrimidinimino isatin lead compound as a novel non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor with broad-spectrum chemotherapeutic properties. Compound 1-ethyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7[[N4-[30-(40-amino-50-trimethoxybenzylpyrimidin-20-yl)imino-10-(5-fluoroisatiny)] methyl]-N1-piperazinyl]-3-quinoline carboxylic acid emerged as the most potent broad-spectrum chemotherapeutic agent active against HIV, HCV, Mycobacterium tuberculosis and various pathogenic bacteria [10].

1-ethyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7[[N4-[30-(40-amino-50-trimethoxybenzylpyrimidin-20-yl)imino-10-(5-fluoroisatiny)] methyl]-N1-piperazinyl]-3-quinoline carboxylic acid

Shuguang Chen et al reported thirty-two quinoline derivatives, designed and synthesized as HIV-1 Tat-TAR interaction inhibitors. All the compounds showed high antiviral activities in inhibiting the formation of SIV-induced syncytium in CEM174 cells. Nine compounds with low cytotoxicities were evaluated by Tat dependent HIV-1 LTR-driven CAT gene expression colorimetric enzyme assay in human 293T cells, it indicates inhibitory activities of blocking the Tat-TAR interaction. Molecular modeling experiments shown that these compounds may inhibit Tat-TAR interaction by binding to Tat protein instead of TAR RNA [11].

$R^1 = \text{H}, -\text{CH}_2\text{Ph}, -\text{CH}_3, -\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2, -\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2, -\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$

$R^2 = -\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}, -\text{COOCH}_3$

Substituted Quinoline 3 Carboxamide

Luca Sancineto et al designed three hybrid molecules combining WM5, a quinolone derivative, previously identified as HIV Tat-mediated transcription (TMT) inhibitor, with the tricyclic core of nevirapine and BILR 355BS (BILR) non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIs) to investigate possibility to obtain molecules acting on both transcription steps of the HIV replicative cycle. One of the compound achieved this goal. Where as compound 1 inhibited both TMT and reverse transcriptase (RT) activity. The anti-TMT activity shown by compound 1 resulted into a selective inhibition of HIV-1 reactivation from latently infected cells, the anti-RT properties shown by all of the synthesized compounds did not translate into an anti-HIV activity in infected cells. They concluded that the design of dual TMT-RT inhibitors is possible subject to optimization efforts are needed to obtain more potent derivatives [12].

Compound No. 1.

Christophe Benard et al studied a novel series of HIV-1 integrase inhibitors. These quinoline inhibitors are designed with aromatic ring linked by functionalized spacers such as amide, hydrazide, urea and 1-hydroxyprop-1-en-3 one moiety. Amide derivatives shown good activity and lead for further developments [13].

(E)-2-(3,4-dihydroxystyryl)-8-hydroxyquinoline-7-carboxylic acid

L. Gupta et al reported chalcones as natural compound belonging to the flavonoid family. A series of chalcone derivatives with quinoline nucleus have been synthesized for potential anti-HIV activity [14].

Substituted Quinoliny Chalcones

Liming Hu et al reported a series of novel 6-(pyrazolylmethyl)-4-oxo-4H-quinoline-3-carboxylic acid derivatives. Quinoline ring were designed with different substituents on the N-position and synthesized as potential HIV-1 integrase (IN) inhibitors, structurally similar to scaffold GS-9137. Also reported detailed synthetic protocols and the anti-IN activity [15].

6-(Pyrazolylmethyl)-4-quinoline-3-carboxylic Acid Derivatives

GS - 9137

Xi-Wen ZENG et al synthesized 5, 5-(p-phenylenebisazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline sulfonates and evaluated as HIV-1 inhibitors. 5,5(p-phenylenebisazo)-8 hydroxy quinoline p-ethyl benzenesulfonate and 5,5-(p-phenylenebisazo)-8 hydroxy quinoline p-chloro benzenesulfonate showed the potent anti-HIV-1 activity [16].

Potent Compounds

Roberto Di Santo et al reported quinolinonyl diketo acids as integrase inhibitors selectively active against the strand transfer step of the HIV integration process. The following compounds are the most potent. Selective inhibition of strand transfer suggested that the monofunctional diketo acids bind the integrase DNA acceptor site without affecting the DNA donor site [17].

(Z)-4-(8-fluoro-1-(4-fluorobenzyl)-4-oxo-1,4-dihydroquinolin-3-yl)-2-hydroxy-4-oxobut-2-enoic acid

(Z)-4-(1-(4-fluorobenzyl)-4-oxo-7-(pyrrolidin-1-yl)-1,4-dihydroquinolin-3-yl)-2-hydroxy-4-oxobut-2-enoic acid

Cristina Parolin et al reported WM5, 6-aminoquinolone derivative shown potent activity against replication of human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) in de novo-infected human lymphoblastoid cells. Further investigated WM5's mechanism of antiviral activity. When the effects of WM5 on different steps of the virus life cycle were analyzed, the reverse transcriptase activity and the integrase and protease activities were not impaired. By using a transient trans-complementation assay the activity of WM5 was examined on the replicative potential of HIV-1 in a single round of infection and found a sustained inhibition of Tat-mediated long terminal repeat (LTR)-driven transcription. Interestingly, the aminoquinolone was found to efficiently complex TAR RNA. The data showed that WM5 is a promising lead compound for the development of a new class of HIV-1 transcription inhibitors characterized by recognition of viral RNA targets [18].

6-amino-1-methyl-4-oxo-7-(4-(pyridin-2-yl)piperazin-1-yl)-1,4-dihydroquinoline-3-carboxylic acid

WM5

Roberto Di Santo et al concluded that the virally encoded integrase protein is an essential enzyme in the life cycle of the HIV-1 virus and represents an attractive and validated target in the development of therapeutics against HIV infection. Drugs as inhibitors of reverse transcriptase and protease, are believed to be highly effective in suppressing the viral replication. Among the HIV-1 integrase inhibitors, the β -diketo acids (DKAs) represent a major lead for anti-HIV-1 drug development. Inhibitors were designed as a novel bifunctional quinolonyl diketo acid derivatives and synthesized and tested for their inhibitory ability against HIV-1 integrase. The compounds are found potent inhibitors of integrase activity. Particularly, following compound is a potent IN inhibitor for both steps of the reaction (3'-processing and strand transfer) and exhibits both high antiviral activity against HIV-1 infected cells and low cytotoxicity. Plausible mechanism of action is provided by molecular modeling studies which is consistent with ligand SARs and enzyme photo-crosslinking experiments [19].

(2Z,2'Z)-4,4'-(1-(4-fluorophenyl)-4-oxo-1,4-dihydroquinoline-3,6-diyl)bis(2-hydroxy-4-oxobut-2-enoic acid)

Virginie Suchaud et al reported the synthesis of series of 3-hydroxyquinolin-2(1H)-one derivatives. Basic scaffold is substituted at fourth position by Esters and amide groups and some modulations of the benzenic moiety were performed and compounds showed selective inhibitory properties against HIV-1 reverse transcriptase associated ribonuclease H activity, without affecting the integrase and reverse transcriptase DNA polymerase activities. Unfortunately all tested compounds showed high cellular cytotoxicity in cell culture due to this their applications as antiviral agents are very limited [20].

Substituted 3-hydroxyquinoline-2(1H)-one

Zhengqiang Wang et al designed and synthesized a series of pyrimidine and a quinolone moiety. The results shown that the compounds are both anti-RT activity and anti-IN activity and useful as scaffold for identifying inhibitors with balanced dual activities [21].

Substituted Pyrimidine and Quinolone Dual Inhibitor

Sammy Metobo et al reported a series of C3 halobenzyl-substituted tricyclic HIV integrase inhibitors. The cell-based inhibitory potency was observed as compared to previously reported tricyclic pyrroloquinolines carrying the 'halobenzyl tail' at the lactam nitrogen. Animal pharmacokinetic study for many C3-substituted inhibitors was examined, with a dihaloaryl analogs [22].

Benzyl Flipped, Tricyclic Pyrroloquinoline Inhibitors

Masahiko Hagihara *et al* reported synthesis and anti-HIV activity of a series of novel aryl piperazinyl fluoroquinolones. The SAR study shown that the aryl substituents on the piperazine nitrogen is important for anti-HIV-1 activity. A few of the compounds exhibited potent anti-HIV activity: Compound R-71762 inhibited HIV-1 replication both in acutely and in chronically infected cells [23].

R 71762

Serena Massari *et al* reported the 6-desfluoroquinolones which represented a promising class of compounds for the treatment of HIV infection. They are acting on transcriptional regulation, a crucial step in the replication cycle. Study focused attention on the N-1 and C-6 positions and a novel series of quinolones has been synthesized. According to SAR study particularly the hydroxyl group emerged as a suitable C-6 substituent when coupled with the appropriate aryl piperazine at the neighboring C-7 position. 6-hydroxyquinolones HM12 and HM13 (6-desfluoroquinolones) were shown very potent activity and selectivity on HIV-1 acutely infected MT-4, CEM and peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) [24].

Qiu-Qin He *et al* synthesized a series of quinolone-3-carboxylic acid substituted with hydroxyl group at C-5 position and evaluated for their in vitro activity against HIV. The most active compound 2k exhibited activity against wild-type HIV-1. Synthesized quinolone analogues were also investigated through preliminary structure-activity relationship study. Further docking study also shown that the anti-HIV activity of these compounds might involve a two-metal chelating mechanism [25].

6-(2,fluoro-3-chlorobenzyl)-5-hydroxy-1-(1-hydroxy-3-methylbutan-2-yl)-4-oxo-1,4-dihydroquinoline-3-carboxylic acid

2K

Qiu-Qin He and Xuan Zhang reported a series of new 5-hydroxyquinolone-3-carboxylic acid with various aryl or benzyl substituents on N-1 position were synthesized and evaluated for their anti-HIV activity. The most active compound exhibited activity against wild-type HIV-1 and HIV-1 mutant virus. The biological results and the docking study shown that the substitution on N-1 position of the quinolone moiety might contribute to physicochemical properties of 5-hydroxyquinolone-3-carboxylic acid and resulted in great influence on their antiviral potency [26].

1-benzyl-6-(2-fluoro-3-chlorobenzyl)-5-hydroxy-4-oxo-1,4-dihydroquinoline-3-carboxylic acid

Potent Compound

Zai Gang Luo et al synthesized and screened a series of novel 6-sulfamoyl-4-oxoquinoline-3-carboxylic acids derivatives as HIV integrase inhibitors. Following compounds showed inhibitory activity against HIV integrase [27].

6-(*N,N*-bis(2-chloroethyl)sulfamoyl)-4-oxo-1,4-dihydroquinoline-3-carboxylic acid

Qiu-Qin He et al reported a series of new quinolone-3-carboxylic acids as HIV-1 integrase inhibitors featuring a fluorine atom at C-5 position were synthesized and evaluated for their antiviral activity. These compounds showed anti-HIV activity against wild-type virus. The most potent compound was found 4e. Preliminary structure-activity relationship of these Compounds (5-fluoroquinolone-3-carboxylic acids) also studied through their structure activity relationship [28].

R = 2*S*-1-hydroxy-3-methylbutan-2-yl

Potent Compound (4e)

Fudi Zhong et al reported Human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) Rev protein facilitates the export of viral RNA from nucleus to cytoplasm, which is a key step in HIV-1 pathogenesis and transmission. In this study, they have screened a commercial library and identified the hit compound bearing a benzenesulfonamide quinoline scaffold that inhibited Rev activity and HIV-1 infectivity. Compounds bearing this scaffold were synthesized and their SAR was studied. Authors identified following compound with low toxicity and potent activity to inhibit HIV-1 replication by affecting Rev function [29].

N-Ethyl-2,4-difluoro-N-(quinolin-8-yl)benzenesulfonamide.

Andrew L. Hopkins *et al* have used a structure-based approach to design a novel series of non-nucleoside inhibitors of HIV-1 RT (NNRTIs). Detailed analysis of a wide range of crystal structures of HIV-1 RT NNRTI complexes together with data on drug resistance mutations has identified factors important for tight binding of inhibitors and resilience to mutations. Using this approach authors have designed and synthesized a novel series of quinolone NNRTIs. Crystal structure analysis of four of these compounds in complexes with HIV-1 RT confirms the predicted binding modes. Members of this quinolone series retain high activity against the important resistance mutations in RT at Tyr181Cys and Leu100Ile. 6-Chloro-4-cyclohexyloxy-3-propylquinol-2-one is the most active [30].

6-chloro-4-cyclohexyloxy-3-propylquinol-2-one

George A. Freeman *et al* reported that HIV-1 non nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIs) are part of the combination therapy currently used to treat HIV infection. The features of a new NNRTI drug for HIV treatment must include selective potent activity against both wild-type virus as well as against mutant virus that have been selected by use of current antiretroviral treatment regimens. Based on analogy with known HIV-1 NNRTI inhibitors and modeling studies utilizing the X-ray crystal structure of inhibitors bound in the HIV-1 RT, a series of substituted 2-quinolones was synthesized and evaluated as HIV-1 inhibitors. Analogues 1ee and 1ff demonstrated the most broad-spectrum activity among these analogues and were more potent than nevirapine and delavirdine against mutant viruses that generally are insensitive to currently known NNRTIs [31].

Compound No. 1ee.

Compound No. 1ff.

Motohide Sato *et al* reported the viral enzyme integrase is essential for the replication of human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) and represents a remaining target for antiretroviral drugs. Here, authors described the modification of a quinolone antibiotic to produce the novel integrase inhibitor JTK-303 (GS 9137) that blocks strand transfer by the viral enzyme. It shares the core structure of quinolone antibiotics, exhibits an IC₅₀ of 7.2 nM in the strand transfer assay, and shows an EC₅₀ of 0.9 nM in an acute HIV-1 infection assay [32].

JTK-303 (GS 9137)

Muriel Billamboz *et al* reported the synthesis of a series of 19, 2-hydroxyisoquinoline-1,3 (2H,4H)-dione derivatives variously substituted at position 7 aimed at inhibiting selectively two-metal ion catalytic active sites. The compounds were tested against HIV-1 reverse transcriptase (RT) polymerase, HIV-1 RT ribonuclease H (RNase H), and HIV-1 integrase (IN). Most compounds displayed poor inhibition of RT polymerase even at 50 μM. The majority of the synthesized compounds inhibited RNase H and IN at micromolar concentrations, and some of them were weakly selective for IN. Surprisingly, two new hits were discovered, which displayed a high selectivity for IN with submicromolar IC₅₀ values. These enzymatic inhibitory properties may be related to the metal binding abilities of the compounds. Physicochemical studies were consistent with a 1/1 stoichiometry of the magnesium complexes in solution, and the metal complexation was strictly dependent on the enolization abilities of the compounds. Unfortunately, all tested compounds exhibited high cellular cytotoxicity in cell culture which limits their applications as antiviral agents. RNase H inhibitors. 6m and 6n with high IC₅₀ RNase H/IC₅₀ HIV-1 IN ratios of 889 and 271, respectively, are the compounds which are the most selective for HIV-1 IN since they are highly potent HIV-1 IN inhibitors and, on the other hand, inactive as RNase H inhibitors [33].

Compound No. 6m

Compound No. 6n

Muriel Billamboz et al reported the synthesis of a series of fifteen 2-hydroxyisoquinoline-1,3(2H,4H)-dione derivatives. Alkyl and arylalkyl groups were introduced on position 4 of the basis scaffold. All the compounds presented poor inhibitory properties against HIV-1 reverse transcriptase ribonuclease H (RNase H). Four compounds inhibited HIV-1 integrase at a low micromolar level. A docking study using the later crystallographic data available for PFV integrase allowed us to explain the slightly improved integrase inhibitory activities of 4-pentyl and 4-(3-phenylpropyl)-2-hydroxyisoquinoline-1,3(2H,4H)-diones, when compared to the basis scaffold. Physicochemical studies were consistent with 1:1 and 1:2 (metal/ligand) stoichiometries of the magnesium complexes in solution. Unfortunately all tested compounds exhibited high cellular cytotoxicity in cell culture which limited their applications as antiviral agents. However these identified integrase inhibitors provide a very good basis for the development of new hits. Introduction of various linear alkyl chains or of alkaryl groups at position 4 led to the identification of four moderate IN inhibitors at micromolar level (5a, 5f, 5j and 5m) [34].

Compound No. 5a

Compound No.5f

Compound No. 5j

Compound No.5m

Sohrab Ghanei et al reported that, the chemistry of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehydes have biological effects as non-nucleoside Human HIV-1 Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors. A group of 2-chloro-3-((2,2-dimethylhydrazono) methyl) quinolone derivatives were synthesized, and theoretically evaluated for their inhibitory as non-nucleoside Human HIV-1 Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors via docking process. Compounds 3g and 3b showed the best inhibitory potency. Some of the best models formed strong hydrogen bonds with Lys 103 via quinoline moiety. It was found that both hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions are important in the structure and function of biological molecules, especially for inhibition in a complex [35].

Compound No. 3b

Compound No. 3g

Monge A et al reported the synthesis and preliminary evaluation of new benzo[f]quinoline and pyridine derivatives, as HIV-1 RT inhibitors and anti-infectives. The most active products against HIV-1 RT wild type are the ethyl 2-cyano-1,2-dihydrobenzo[f]quinoline-1-carboxylate, propyl 2-cyano-1,2-dihydrobenzo [f] quinoline-1-carboxylate, and 2-cyano-1-(2'-furoyl)-1,2-dihydro benzo [f] quinoline. Using the data previously obtained by their research team for analogous series derived from quinoline as reference, the compounds which have now been obtained present an increase in the cytotoxic character attributable to the introduction of a benzene ring fused with the quinoline base nucleus, as well as a decrease of the activity as HIV-1 RT inhibitors when the quinoline benzenic ring is eliminated [36].

Khalid Mekouar et al reported that on the basis of the fact that several polynucleotidyl transferases, related to HIV integrase, contain in their active site two divalent metal cations, separated by ca. 4 Å, new potential HIV integrase inhibitors were designed, in which a quinoline substructure is linked to an aryl nucleus possessing various hydroxy substitution patterns, by means of an ethylenic spacer. Although the most active compounds contain the catechol structure, this group is not essential for the activity, since compound 21 that lacks such a moiety is a potent drug, implicating the presence of a different pharmacophore. The most promising styrylquinolines thus synthesized inhibit HIV-1 integrase in vitro at micromolar or submicromolar concentrations and block HIV replication in CEM cells, with no significant cellular toxicity in a 5-day period assay. These inhibitors are active against integrase core domain-mediated disintegration, suggesting that fragment 50 -212 is their actual target. These new styrylquinolines may provide lead compounds for the development of novel antiretroviral agents for AIDS therapeutics, based upon inhibition of HIV integrase. They might also be used in the elucidation of the mechanism of inhibition of this enzyme; e.g., they could serve as candidates for cocrystallization studies with HIV integrase [37].

Compound No. 21

S. Murugesan et al synthesized a novel series of fifteen 3-(3, 4-dihydro isoquinolin-2(1H)-yl)-N-(substituted phenyl) propanamides. All the compounds were evaluated for their HIV-1 RT inhibitory activity. Among the synthesized compounds, 3-(3, 4-dihydro isoquinolin-2(1H)-yl)-N-o-tolyl propanamide 3d and 3-(3, 4-dihydro isoquinolin-2(1H)-yl)-N-(2, 4, 6-tribromo phenyl) propanamide 3f were identified as significant inhibitors of HIV-1 reverse transcriptase. Docking studies with HIV-1 RT (PDB ID 1rt2) were also performed in order to investigate the binding pattern of these compounds [38].

Compound No. 3d

Compound No. 3f

CONCLUSION

The human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) has established as the causative agent of the acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) for over many years. The currently Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved anti-HIV drugs and divided into seven groups: nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NRTIs), nucleotide reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NRTIs), non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIs), protease inhibitors (PIs) etc. However, the use of these drugs has been relatively limited by their toxicity, drug resistance development, and more worryingly, the fact that some newly HIV-infected patients carry viruses that are already resistant to the currently approved AIDS treatments. These issues along with drug-related side effects as well as, in some cases, poor tolerability of these drugs make it apparent that new anti-HIV drugs with acceptable toxicity and resistance profiles and, more importantly, new anti-HIV agents with novel mechanisms of action are clearly needed. An approach of combination therapy was developed which involved combining several antiretroviral compounds. This marked the beginning of the era of highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART). Combinations of antiretrovirals create multiple barriers to the HIV replication process. This helps to keep the number of offspring low and reduce the possibility of a superior mutation. HAART suffers from certain limitations, despite of its success. HAART therapy is highly effective in delaying the onset of AIDS but its clinical utility is limited by viral resistance, non-adherence to therapy, and drug toxicity. Consequently, multidrug regimens are necessary for successful treatment. Here identified several quinoline scaffold derivatives with excellent physicochemical and pharmacological properties that represent interesting candidates for further development as antiHIV agents.

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Conflict of interests:

Authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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